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Abstract:

SSHOC Deliverable 5.7 is a report on the impact of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on research and its possible implications for EOSC. This deliverable describes and compares national implementation of the GDPR across Europe by examining the national laws of a few randomly selected European countries, and by conducting interviews with a few researchers in three of these countries. The report also describes implications the GDPR might have for EOSC.

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Executive Summary

Background: The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (hereinafter referred to as GDPR or the Regulation)¹ has given European countries a unique opportunity to harmonize their legal framework, and to improve the conditions for research and cross-border data flow. Although one of the rationales behind the GDPR was to harmonize the legal framework for data processing to improve conditions for research and cross-border data flow. This represents both risks and opportunities.

Main aim: Deliverable “5.7 Report on the impact of the GDPR and its implications for EOSC” of the Horizon 2020 project “Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud” (hereinafter referred to as “SSHOC”, GA Number 823785) examines the impact of the GDPR and possible implications for EOSC. The main aim of this deliverable is to describe and compare national implementation of the GDPR in a few randomly selected countries.

Methodology: The national implementation of the GDPR with focus on research in Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany, and Italy is described and compared. The first four countries were chosen as their national privacy legislation has been a subject to review in a previous not published report. Germany and Italy, on the other hand, were chosen as they had relevant national legislation available in understandable language. The deliverable also addresses the case of UK and the GDPR, with focus on how “Brexit” can affect cross border data flow between EU/EEA countries and the UK. The articles in the GDPR with the highest relevance for research conditions were included, interpretations and solutions of the GDPR were investigated, and 14 researchers were interviewed regarding their experience with the GDPR and how the GDPR has affected the research environment.

Main outcome: Some of the selected countries have implemented provisions in their national legislation that are beneficial for research, whilst some have not focused on research as a task in the public interest. Furthermore, there seems to be different interpretations from judicial experts on how the law should be interpreted in some countries, as well as different national supplementary provisions, making harmonization more challenging.

¹ Official Journal of the European Union

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN> (11.06.2021)

Conclusion: Results from this deliverable indicate that further work is necessary to improve cross-border data flow within Europe. As the report “Two years of the GDPR: Questions and answers”² concludes, further support of harmonization and consistent implementation of the GDPR across the EU is warranted. This includes making sure that national legislation is fully in line with the GDPR.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

BDSG	Bundesdatenschutzgesetz (Federal Data Protection Act)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EU	European Union
EEA	European Economic Area
EDPB	European data protection board
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
LED	Law and Enforcement Directive

² European Commission (2020) “Two years of the GDPR: Questions and answers”
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_20_1166 (downloaded 12.08.2020)

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1 Introduction

The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)³ has given European countries a unique opportunity to harmonize their legal framework, and to improve the conditions for research and cross-border data flow. One of the rationales behind the new regulation is to ensure the same level of data protection throughout the EU to facilitate open access and reusability of research data. Thus, the GDPR has a limited flexibility in its application. Nevertheless, the Regulation leaves room for national supplementary provisions, including derogations, and this possibility applies especially to the field of research. This represents both risks and opportunities.

According to the report «Two years of the GDPR: Questions and answers», published on 24 of June 2020 by the EU Commission, the implementation of the GDPR has been a success. The report concludes that harmonization across the Member States is increasing, although there is a certain level of fragmentation that must be continually monitored. Further, the report states that it is important to further support harmonization and consistent implementation of the GDPR across the EU. This includes making sure that national legislation is fully in line with the GDPR. To facilitate harmonization across Member States and sectors, the report highlights creation and use of Codes of Conducts as an important tool to ensure such harmonization.⁴

This deliverable describes and compares national implementation of the GDPR with focus on research in Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Finland, Germany, and Italy. Some of the information from the Nordic countries stems from an unpublished report written by a Nordic network project, funded by the Norwegian research Council, where task member NSD – Norwegian Centre for Research Data was a leading partner. This deliverable compares the national data protection legislations in the mentioned countries and analyses whether they are beneficial for research and archival purposes, based on the project teams interpretations of the national legislation. It also addresses the case of UK and the GDPR, with focus on how “Brexit” can affect cross border data flow between EU/EEA countries and the UK.

In addition, the T5.3 partners present results from interviews with 14 researchers from three European countries (Denmark, Norway, and Italy), to get a deeper understanding on how the GDPR has affected their research and conditions for across border cooperation and data flow.

³ EUR LEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=EN> [accessed 12.06.2021]

⁴ European Commission (2020) “Two years of the GDPR: Questions and answers” - https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_20_1166 [accessed 12.08.2020]

By comparing national supplementary legislation and conducting interviews in selected countries, this deliverable also identifies some aspects that might have implications for EOSC.

2 Methodology

The main purpose of SSHOC project is to create the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) area of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), thereby facilitating access to flexible, scalable research data, and related services streamlined to the precise needs of the SSH community. The focus of the task 5.3 Legal Issues of Innovative Data Access, accordingly, is on the provisions within the GDPR, which are suggested to have the highest relevance and impact on research conditions.

The articles with highest relevance and impact on research conditions within the GDPR are presented in this report. Thereafter, the report investigates and describes how the selected countries have implemented these articles, making it possible to compare the implementation in selected countries. Further, the report discusses variations of interpretations in selected countries and how that may influence research in general, and data sharing and cross-border research in particular. A discussion and analysis of legislation prior to adopting the GDPR in different countries along with differences concerning special legislation falls outside of the scope of this report.

Following articles within the GDPR were selected:

- Lawfulness of processing – Art. 6 (1)(e),
- Processing of special categories of personal data – Art. 9 (2)(j),
- Appropriate safeguards – Art. 89 (1),
- Processing of data relating to criminal convictions and offences – Art. 10.

The first three articles cover the legal basis for processing of personal data related to general and special categories of personal data. Further, as the GDPR explicitly regulates processing of data related to criminal convictions and offences, processing of such data is covered in a separate section in this report, given that sharing of such data can only take place if the researchers are placed in a country where required supplementary national legislation has been given, thereby allowing for such processing. This also means that if data related to criminal convictions and offences are included in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), that would have implications for the accessibility of these data.

A broad analysis on how the implementation of the GDPR has been functioning in practice, both in general and within the selected countries, falls outside of the scope of this report. However, the task force has conducted interviews with 14 researchers in three randomly selected countries (Denmark, Norway, and Italy), based on an interview guide developed for this study. The interview questions aim to

get a deeper understanding of the GDPR implications on daily lives of researchers⁵. Invitation to participate was sent to researchers from different research fields having experiences with conducting research before and after GDPR entered into force. Most of the available interview subjects were health researchers. Considering that the GDPR permits or requires Member States to implement specifications or restrictions on certain rules the interpretation of it will not create identical privacy and data protection rules across all Member States. This means that, although European data protection laws are more harmonised under the GDPR than previously, national variations remain. Interviews with researchers from other Member States or with different experiences could shed light on other conventions.

It is important to address that the findings in this report cannot be generalised to all EU/EEA countries and to the research environment in general. The assessment of national implementation has only been conducted in the selected countries and findings from the interviews represent only a few selected researchers' experiences and opinions. A broader analysis on how the implementation of GDPR has been functioning in practice, both within EU/EEA countries and compared to each other, could be subject to further work in T8.3 Legal and Ethical Issues.

This deliverable focuses on the judicial aspect of the GDPR and how the GDPR, to a certain extent, is implemented in practice, and within the field of research. This is to get a better understanding on how both the judicial side and how the human interpretations can affect the implementation of the GDPR and its implications. Comparing national legislation might show some legal implications for EOSC, whilst the interview might also identify some general implications. Consequently, in this deliverable it has been decided to differ between juridical implications and general implications for EOSC. Juridical implications for EOSC are discussed after the presentation of provisions within the GDPR and national supplementation to legal basis, while general implications for EOSC are discussed after presenting the findings from interviewing researchers. However, it is sometimes hard to differ among these "chapters", as they often affect each other. Furthermore, this report does not provide an exhaustive list of implications for EOSC. Instead, it rather provides some possible implications identified by the task 5.3 force.

⁵ See the enclosed interview (interview questions) in section 8.

3 Processing personal data based on a public interest

There are six available lawful bases for processing such personal data. Most appropriate use depends on the purpose of the processing. Article 6 – Lawfulness of Processing ⁶.

The lawful bases are presented as follows.

In GDPR Article 6 (1)⁷ it is stated that:

“1. Processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies:

- (a) the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes;
- (b) processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract;
- (c) processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject;
- (d) processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person;
- (e) processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller;
- (f) processing is necessary for the purpose of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.”

Further, the following is stated in Article 6 (2) and (3), supplementing Article 6 (1):

“2. Member States may maintain or introduce more specific provisions to adapt the application of the rules of this Regulation with regard to processing for compliance with points (c) and (e) of paragraph 1

⁶ GDPR: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁷ GDPR: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

by determining more precisely specific requirements for the processing and other measures to ensure lawful and fair processing including for other specific processing situations as provided for in Chapter IX.

3. The basis for processing referred to in point (c) and (e) of paragraph 1 shall be laid down by:

(a) Union law; or

(b) Member States law to which the controller is subject.

The purpose of the processing shall be determined in that legal basis or, as regards the processing referred to in point (e) of paragraph 1, shall be necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller. That legal basis may contain specific provisions to adapt the application of rules of this Regulation, inter alia: the general conditions governing the lawfulness of processing by the controller; the types of data which are subject to the processing; the data subjects concerned; the entities to, and the purpose for which, the personal data may be disclosed; the purpose limitation; storage periods; and processing operations and processing procedures, including measures to ensure lawful and fair processing such as those for other specific processing situations as provided for in Chapter IX. The Union or the Member State law shall meet an objective of public interest and be proportionate to the legitimate aim pursued.”⁸

This section explores Article 6.1 (e), which is considered most appropriate to use for research purposes, alongside consent Article 6.1 (a). Article 6.1 (e) states that it is allowed to process personal data if the purpose is in the public interest.

As presented above, the GDPR allows Member states to maintain or introduce more specific or supplementary provisions when processing personal data for research or archival purposes, in accordance with the legal basis “in the public interest” in Article 6.1(e). Article 6.2 states that public interest as lawful basis “may” be issued by Union or Member state law, thereby giving national legislators a margin for issuing national legislation for processing of personal data subject to Article 6.1 (e).

The wording of the term “may” imply that the issuing of national provisions is optional. This interpretation is supported by the wording in GDPR Article 9.2 (j)⁹, where the processing is preconditioned to be based on Member State law. However, it seems to be an inferred understanding, at least amongst most of the Nordic countries, that Article 6.1(e) imposes the Member State to issue further legislation for the processing in the public interest.

⁸ GDPR: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁹ GDPR: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

The following paragraphs will discuss how the selected countries have interpreted the reference to these “more specific provisions”, cf. GDPR Article 6.1 (e)¹⁰. A summary of the results is shown in Table 1.

3.1 Sweden

The Swedish Data protection act (“Dataskyddlagen”¹¹) chapter 2, § 2 (1) determines a supplementary provision for processing data with the basis in Article 6. 1(e), when necessary to carry out a task in the public interest based on formal law or other legal material, based on a collective agreement, or a decision made based on law/other legislative material.

The government leaves § 2, chapter 2 of the General Data Protection Act¹² to fulfil the requirement of a national legal basis for processing of personal data for research purposes. According to the government, the term “laid down” does not require a specific provision for each processing, but rather that the task carried out in the public interest – the task to carry out research – must have a legal basis in national law. For private bodies, this requirement will be fulfilled if the project has been approved according to the Ethical Review Act. In order for research conducted by public authorities to be lawful, the national basis shall be laid down in national law, for example will research conducted by public universities and colleges be regarded as “laid down” in the College Act (Högskolelagen¹³), or, if conducted by counties or municipalities acting as legal persons, when decided in accordance with the Municipality Act.

The Data protection Act of Sweden chapter 2, § 3 (1) states that the government can issue provisions/regulations allowing bodies not included by the archival laws to process data for archival purposes in the public interest.

Furthermore, paragraph two states that the government may decide that bodies as referenced in paragraph one may process personal data for archive purposes in the public interest in individual cases.

¹⁰ GDPR: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

¹¹ Riksdagen: https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2018218-med-kompletterande-bestammelser_sfs-2018-218 [accessed 23.06.2021]

¹² Riksdagen: https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2018218-med-kompletterande-bestammelser_sfs-2018-218 [accessed 23.06.2021]

¹³ Riksdagen: https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/hogskolelag-19921434_sfs-1992-1434 [accessed 23.06.2021]

3.2 Finland

Finland passed a supplementary implementation act of the GDPR, the Data protection Act of Finland¹⁴, which entered into force on January 1, 2019.

The act has two explicit legal bases for the processing of general personal data for research purposes, and for archival purposes in the public interest, in §§ 4.3 and 4.4. The provisions are based on Article 6.2, to clarify the application of the term processing of personal data “in the public interest” of Article 6.1 (e). Both these legal bases include a test of proportionality and necessity.

3.3 Denmark

The Danish Data Protection Act¹⁵ § 6, states that personal data may be processed when the processing meets the requirements of Article 6.1 letters (a)-(f). The Act deliberates on the meaning of the wording in Article 6.2 and 6.3, referring to “Union (...) or Member State law”, and decides that the Regulation does not impose issuing a specific statute for every processing. Thus, a statute allowing multiple processing for the fulfilment of a task in the public interest is deemed sufficient. The conclusion seems to be that article 6.1(e) is deemed to be directly applicable, as long as the controller is performing a task carried out in the public interest, or in the exercise of public authority. A national, implementing legal basis of the processing itself is, therefore, not required when processing personal data for the performance of a task in the public interest or in the exercise of public authority.

The Danish Data Protection Act § 10 regulates the processing of special categories of personal data based on statistical and scientific purposes. However, in § 10, stk. 2 it is stated that data mentioned in paragraph 10, stk. 1, cannot be further processed for other than scientific or statistical purposes. Further, it is mentioned that the same applies for data mentioned in the GDPR Article 6, when being processed based on statistical or scientifically purposes. This is further elaborated in this deliverable when presenting § 10.

As for archival purposes, chapter 3, § 14, of the Danish Data Protection Act, states that personal data can be archived in accordance with the national archive legislation.

¹⁴ FINLEX: <https://www.finlex.fi/sv/laki/alkup/2018/20181050> [accessed 23.06.2021]

¹⁵ Retsinformation.dk: <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2018/502> [accessed 23.06.2021]

3.4 Norway

The Personal Data Act of Norway¹⁶ determines the need for national supplementary provisions when processing data pursuant to Article 6.1(e), referring to the provisions of Article 6.3 paragraph one. This results in § 8, paragraph one, stating that processing of personal data subject to Article 6.1 (e), is lawful, if necessary, for historical and scientific research purposes, statistical purposes, or archival purposes in the public interest. Furthermore, § 8 refers to the duty to determine appropriate safeguards in accordance with Article 89.1.

3.5 Germany

From 25/05/2018, the GDPR and the new Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG new¹⁷) together ensure the protection of the fundamental right to informational self-determination in Germany. There is no explicit mentioning of Article 6.1 (e) in BDSG.

This indicates that Germany has interpreted the issuing of a national provision as optional, and therefore has not issued further legislation for the processing of data in the public interest. There are however explicit mentions of the processing of special categories of personal data for research and archiving purposes without consent. A conclusion can be drawn that one cannot process special categories of personal data without also processing general categories of personal data. Furthermore, that research and archiving are in the public interest.

3.6 Italy

As far as the task team has been able to establish, there has not been a total repeal of the Privacy Code in Italy following the implementation of the GDPR.¹⁸

The Italian 2018 Budget Law¹⁹ states that data controllers that process personal data through automated means or “new technologies” based on legitimate interest (Article 6. 1 (f)) is obligated to send notification to the Italian Supervisory Authority prior to processing of personal data and wait 15 days for the approval

¹⁶ Lovdata.no: <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

¹⁷ <https://dsgvo-gesetz.de/bdsg/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

¹⁸ Note that all Italian legal sources are based on oral communication and non-English versions, and that the legal situation might not be correctly presented in this report. These issues can be further explored in task 8.3 Legal and Ethical issues.

¹⁹ Law no. 205 of 27 December 2017

(before commencing processing). During the 15 days, the Supervisory Authority shall investigate and decide whether to approve, suspend or even to stop the processing where the interests of the data controller are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subjects.

This kind of provision does not fall within the scope of discretionary power granted to Member States by the GDPR, where the requirement for a prior check by the supervisory authority as stated in the Directive/95²⁰ has been replaced by the principle of accountability that characterizes the entire GDPR.

Article 6 affects Title V of Part II of the Italian Personal Data Protection Code (also known as the Italian Code of Privacy²¹), which concerns the processing of personal data in the health sector. In the report accompanying the provision, it is emphasized that the new Articles reproduce the current Articles of the Code: the changes are dictated by the need to update certain normative references and to expunge every reference to the consent that, according to the regulation, no longer constitutes the only requirement of lawfulness (legal basis) of data processing. In relation to this part of the Code, Article 27 lists the numerous repealed Articles.

3.7 Summary

A significant part of the research conducted each year is performed without a consent as the legal ground for processing personal data, due to consensual processing being impossible or disproportionately difficult. Thus, from a research point of view, there is a need for a national legal basis that substitutes consensual research, i.e., the lawful processing of personal data “in the public interest”. To summarize, four of six countries examined in this report have implemented a national provision for the lawful processing of personal data for research purposes and archival purposes in the public interest. The Swedish, Danish, Finnish and Norwegian Data Protection Acts ensure a clear legal basis for processing of personal data for those purposes. Germany has not issued a similar provision in its respective national laws. However, Germany has issued a national legal basis for processing special categories of personal data. That indicates that research and archival purposes are indeed important in the public interest. As far as the purpose of this report, the Italian law has not implemented a specific provision indicating that research/archival purposes are in the public interest. The law has, however, clarified that consent is no longer the only legal basis for processing personal data.

²⁰ EURLEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31995L0046&rid=5> [accessed 23.06.2021]

²¹ Garanteprivacy.it: <https://www.garanteprivacy.it/documents/10160/0/Data+Protection+Code.pdf/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

A clear provision in national law stating that research is in the public interest would make it easier for research institutions, as data controllers, to use 6.1 (e) as a legal basis, in cases where consent as a legal basis is not applicable.

TABLE 1 A SUMMARY OF HOW PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA “NECESSARY FOR THE PERFORMANCE OF A TASK CARRIED OUT IN THE PUBLIC INTEREST, ARTICLE 6.1 (E) IS INTERPRETED IN SWEDEN, FINLAND, DENMARK, NORWAY, GERMANY AND ITALY.

Processing of personal data “necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest”, Article 6.1(e).		
	Research	Archive
Sweden	The Data Protection Act, Chapter. 2, § 2(1). <i>When necessary to carry out a task in public interest based on legislative material, a collective agreement or a decision made based on legislative material.</i>	The Data Protection Act, Chapter 2, § 3 (1). <i>The government can issue regulations regarding data processing for archive purposes in the public interest.</i>
Finland	The Data protection Act, Chapter 2, § 4(3). Lawful processing when necessary for scientific/historic research and statistics, when proportionate to the execution of the public interest pursued.	The Data protection Act, Chapter 2, § 4(4). <i>Lawful processing if necessary for archival purposes when proportionate to the execution of the public interest pursued and the rights of the data subject.</i>
Denmark	The Data Protection Act § 6. <i>Lawful processing if requirements of Article 6.1 (e) are met. The processing must have a legitimate foundation in one or several national legal bases. A specific legal basis for each processing is not required.</i>	The Data Protection Act, Chapter 3, § 14. <i>Processing allowed for archival purposes in accordance with national legislation.</i>
Norway	The Data Protection Act, § 8. <i>Processing lawful if necessary for research and statistic purposes in the public interest. Appropriate safeguards in accordance with Article 89.1 must be taken (see Table 3).</i>	The Data Protection Act, § 8. <i>Processing lawful when necessary for archival purposes in the public interest. Appropriate safeguards in accordance with Article 89.1 must be taken (see Table 3).</i>
Germany	No supplementary provision in the BDSG.	No supplementary provision in the BDSG. <i>However, the processing of special categories of personal data for archiving purposes,</i>

	<p><i>However, the processing of special categories of personal data for research purposes, without consent, is mentioned in section 27 in the BDSG.</i></p>	<p><i>without consent, is mentioned in section 28 in the BDSG.</i></p>
Italy	<p>No supplementary provision in the Italian Personal Data Protection Code.</p> <p><i>However, it is clarified that consent is no longer the only legal basis for processing personal data.</i></p>	<p>No supplementary provision in the Italian Personal Data Protection Code.</p>

4 Processing of special categories of personal data

Special categories of personal data are those that need more protection than general categories of personal data because of its sensitive character. The processing of special categories of personal data (e.g., data revealing health, racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs) is prohibited unless there is a specific legal ground to process such data, cf. GDPR art. 9 (1)²². Consequently, in addition to meeting one of the legal basis under Article 6 of the GDPR, processing of special categories of personal data must comply with a separate condition under Article 9.

The GDPR Article 9 (2) states that it is not prohibited to process special categories of personal data “(...) if one of the following applies:

(a) the data subject has given explicit consent to the processing of those personal data for one or more specific purposes, except where Union or Member State law provide that the prohibition referred to in paragraph 1 may not be lifted by the data subject;

(b) processing is necessary for the purpose of carrying out the obligations and exercising specific rights of the controller or of the data subject in the field of employment and social security and social protection law in so far as it is authorised by Union or Member State law or a collective agreement pursuant to Member State law providing for appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject;

(c) processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject or another natural person where the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent;

(d) processing is carried out in the course of its legitimate activities with appropriate safeguards by a foundation, association or any other not-for-profit body with a political, philosophical, religious or trade union aim and on condition that the processing relates solely to the member or to former members of the body or to persons who have regular contact with it in connection with its purposes and that the personal data are not disclosed outside that body without the consent of the data subjects.

(e) processing relates to personal data which are manifestly made public by the data subject;

(f) processing is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defence or legal claims or whenever courts are acting in their judicial capacity;

²² GDPR: <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

(g) processing is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest, on the basis of Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subjects;

(h) processing is necessary for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine, for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, medical diagnosis, the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and services on the basis of Union or Member State law or pursuant to contract with health professional and subject to the conditions and safeguard referrers to in paragraph 3;

(l) processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, such as protecting against serious cross-border threats to health or ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices, on the basis of Union or Member State law which provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject, in particular professional secrecy;

(j) processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) based on Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.

Apart from explicit consent, the most relevant legal basis for research and archival purposes is Article 9.2(j). According to Recital 52²³, research serves as a basis for processing sensitive data only “when provided by Union or Member State law and subject to suitable safeguards.” The processing must be performed in accordance with Article 89. 1. This applies to any processing of sensitive data, including data sharing within and across national borders.

The following paragraphs provide a brief presentation of the various implementations of national legal bases for the processing of personal data, subject to Article 9.2(j) in the mentioned European countries. A summary of the results is presented in **TABLE 2**.

²³ EURLEX: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679> [accessed 23.06.2021]

4.1 Sweden

The Swedish Data Protection Act²⁴ has no specific paragraph stating that special categories of personal data can be processed for research purposes, in accordance with GDPR Article 9.2 (j). However, The Swedish Data Protection Act chapter 3, § 3 (3) determines that authorities in correspondence with GDPR Article 9.2 (g), may process sensitive personal data if necessary for important tasks in the public interest, and that the processing does not involve an undue interference of the integrity of the data subject. The government has pointed out that this relates to public authorities.²⁵

The Swedish Data Protection Act chapter 3, § 4 states that the government may issue provisions regarding processing of special categories of data for fulfilling an “important public interest”.

The processing of special categories of personal data shall according to the Law Council Referral (“Lagrådsremiss²⁶”), be governed by the Ethical Review Act²⁷ § 3, combined with § 6 of the same Act. The Ethical Review Act § 3 states that the act applies to research processing personal data covered by Article 9.1 or personal data mentioned in Article 10. Paragraph 6 states the requirement of ethical approval for research.

The Law Council Referral²⁸ page 87 states that ethical review of research projects is viewed as constituting a “suitable and specific measure”, cf. Article 9.2 (j) for processing of special category of personal data for ²⁹Moreover, the government regards approval according to the Ethical Review Act as a complementary national provision for research purposes in the public interest as required by Article 9.2 (j), cf. page 89 and paragraph 7.2.2 of the Law Council Referral³⁰. It emphasizes that the duty to submit the project to

²⁴ Riksdagen.se: https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2018218-med-kompletterande-bestammelser_sfs-2018-218 [accessed 23.06.2021]

²⁵ Prop.2017/18:105 page 194,

<https://www.regeringen.se/492373/contentassets/561c615d11104ad38c42b59cda9c33bc/ny-dataskyddslag-prop.-201718105> [accessed 23.06.2021]

²⁶ Regeringen.se: <https://www.regeringen.se/4b00ca/contentassets/65ecec1e45b34af0bc1c272e40ccf581/ny-dataskyddslag> [accessed 23.06.2021]

²⁷ Riksdagen.se: https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2003460-om-etikprovning-av-forskning-som_sfs-2003-460 [accessed 23.06.2021]

²⁸ Regeringen.se: <https://www.regeringen.se/4b00ca/contentassets/65ecec1e45b34af0bc1c272e40ccf581/ny-dataskyddslag> [accessed 23.06.2021]

²⁹ Furthermore, it is stated that Ethical Review is a “suitable and specific” measure when processing personal data for research according to the Clinical Trial Regulation (536/2014).

³⁰ Regeringen.se: <https://www.regeringen.se/4b00ca/contentassets/65ecec1e45b34af0bc1c272e40ccf581/ny-dataskyddslag> [accessed 23.06.2021]

ethical review applies irrespectively of the legal basis. This result in a compulsory ethical review in both consent-based and non-consent-, including register-based research.³¹

The Ethical Review Act §§ 7 - 11a constitutes the requirements for lawful processing of special categories of personal data, which, amongst other things, entails attest of necessity and proportionality.

In the Data protection Act of Sweden, Chapter 3, § 6 it is stated that sensitive personal data may be processed for archival purposes in the public interest when necessary to follow regulations on the conservation and care of archives.

Furthermore, the government may issue regulations allowing other than those comprised by the archival laws to process sensitive personal data for archival purposes in the public interest.

4.2 Finland

The Data protection Act of Finland³², §§ 6 (7) and 6 (8) states that sensitive personal data may be processed for scientific/historical research or statistics, and archival purposes in the public interest (except from genetic data) if specific and suitable measures are in place. What is deemed suitable measures in Finland is mentioned in section 5.2, when taking a closer look at safeguards in accordance with article 89.1.

4.3 Denmark

Paragraph 10, stk. 1 of The Data Protection Act³³ states that personal data as mentioned in Article 9.1 may be processed for statistical or scientific investigations of significant importance for society, if necessary, for the conducting of these investigations.

Paragraph 10, stk. 2 states that data mentioned in paragraph 10, stk. 1, cannot be shared for further processing for other purposes than scientific or statistical investigations.

Paragraph 10, stk. 3 of the Danish Act states that data as mentioned in Articles 9 and 10 of the Regulation must not be disclosed to third parties without the approval of the supervisory authority, and that the

³¹ The government does however, stress that the requirement for Ethical review only applies to special categories of personal data and personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, not general personal data.

³² Finlex.fi: <https://www.finlex.fi/sv/laki/alkup/2018/20181050> [accessed 23.06.2021]

³³ <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/lta/2018/502>

authority may set conditions for the disclosing. As in Sweden, research project that process personal data must be approved by an ethical committee.

This means that the protection of sensitive personal data in Denmark to a large extent, still is a matter of ethical and legal review and pre-authorisation. This contrasts with the accountability principle laid down by the GDPR. However, the Danish Supervision Authority has in an Executive order (“Bekendtgørelse”)³⁴ determined when it is considered acceptable sharing personal data in correspondence with § 10 (stk. 1 and 2), without the need of such approval³⁵. In the Executive order § 2³⁶ it is stated that personal data can only be shared, if necessary, for the receivers concrete statistical or scientific purpose. Prior to the extradition, the Controller must make sure that the data only will be used for such purpose³⁷, This requires a written statement from the receiver (e.g., the institution)³⁸. Further, the Controller is obliged to make sure that the receivers’ obligations are met³⁹. This also requires a written statement⁴⁰.

Further, the data can only be given in a pseudonymised manner⁴¹. However, if necessary, for the relevant statistical or scientific purpose, identifiable data might be given (but the receiver must use a scrambling key),⁴². If the sharing of data takes place online, the receiver must make appropriate safety measures⁴³. If special categories of personal data, this means at least encryption⁴⁴. In order to reach the needed level of security proportional to the relevant level of risk, relevant technical and organizational measures must be taken in accordance with the GDPR Article 32⁴⁵.

³⁴ <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

³⁵ <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

³⁶ <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

³⁷ See § 8, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

³⁸ See § 9, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

³⁹ See §§ 8 and 9, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁴⁰ See § 8, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁴¹ See § 3, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁴² See § 4, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

A scrambling key is a list of names or a file that makes identification of individuals possible in a data set. Creating a scrambling key entails removing names, social security number, email-address or other directly identifiable information in a data set, and replacing them with a code, a number, a fictitious name etc., referring to a separate list where each code refers to a specific name.

⁴³ See § 5, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁴⁴ See § 6, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁴⁵ See § 7, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

The receiver's obligations/requirements are regulated in the Executive order Chapter 3, §§ 10 – 14⁴⁶. First, the receiver must be authorized by the Controller⁴⁷. Persons getting access to the data, must be given instructions for the processing (thereby not to process data for other purposes than statistical or scientific investigations)⁴⁸. To reach the needed level of security proportional to the relevant level of risk, relevant technical and organizational measures must be taken in accordance with the GDPR Article 32⁴⁹.. At the end of the statistical or scientific investigation, personal data shall be deleted, be anonymized, get destroyed or be returned to the Controller⁵⁰. The data may also get transferred to archives in correspondence with archive regulations.

4.4 Norway

The Personal Data Act § 9⁵¹ states that special categories of personal data can be processed, if necessary, for archival purposes, and for historical and scientific research purposes, as well as statistical purposes in the public interest, and the societal interest of the processing clearly exceeds the disadvantage imposed on the data subject. Furthermore, the processing shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, c.f. GDPR Article 89.1. In addition to these preliminary conditions, § 9, paragraph two of the Personal Data Act⁵², instructs the controller to consult a data protection officer (DPO) (or the like) prior to the processing, unless the controller has performed a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) in accordance with GDPR Article 35. Upon the consultation, the DPO shall assess whether the planned processing will fulfil the requirements of the Regulation and other provisions in national legislation. The duty to consult the DPO is regarded as mean to ensure “suitable and specific measures” in accordance with GDPR art. 9.2 (j). The duty also applies to consent-based research.

Other than this, the Ministry does not find it expedient to settle these kinds of measures in the law, because each type of processing will require an individual assessment of what measures will be deemed “suitable and specific”.

⁴⁶ <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁴⁷ See § 10, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁴⁸ See § 11, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁴⁹ See § 13, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁵⁰ See § 14, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁵¹ <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁵² <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

4.5 Germany

Processing of special categories of personal data as referred to in GDPR Article 9.1 shall be permitted, also without consent for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, if such processing is necessary for these purposes. Furthermore, if the interests of the controller in processing outweigh those of the data subject in not processing the data⁵³.

In addition to mentioning data processing for research purposes, special categories of personal data can be processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, without consent⁵⁴.

When processing personal data for these purposes without consent, the data controller must make the appropriate measures to protect the personal data⁵⁵. BDSG Section 27(1) implements the GDPR Article 9.2 (j)⁵⁶ in conjunction with the GDPR Article 89(2). This is described in more detail in section 5.5 of this deliverable where GDPR article 89 and appropriate safeguards are discussed in more detail.

4.6 Italy

Italy established Italian current scheme of the legislative decree of harmonization⁵⁷. Article 2-sexies of decree, which refers to GDPR Article 9.1, sets specific conditions for the legitimate processing of special categories of personal data, which are processed for reasons of significant public interest. More specifically, Article 2-sexies of the decree provides that the processing of the special categories of personal data referred to in Article 9.1 of the GDPR⁵⁸, necessary for reasons of significant public interest, pursuant to the letter (g), paragraph 2, of the same Article, are allowed if one of the following is:

- (i) provided for by law of the European Union,
- (ii) provided for by provisions of law (in the internal legal system)

⁵³ See Section 27 (1) “Data processing for purposes of scientific or historical research and for statistical purposes” of the BDSG, <https://dsgvo-gesetz.de/bdsg/>

⁵⁴ See Section 28 of the BDSG, <https://dsgvo-gesetz.de/bdsg/>

⁵⁵ See Section 22 (2) of the BDSG, <https://dsgvo-gesetz.de/bdsg/>

⁵⁶ <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/>

⁵⁷ Please note that all Italian legal sources are based on oral communication and non-English versions, and that the legal situation might not be correctly presented in this report. These issues can be further explored in task 8.3 Legal and Ethical issues.

⁵⁸ <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/>

- (iii) provided for by the operations that can be carried out and the reason of significant public interest (in the cases provided by the law, of regulation specifying the types of data that can be processed)

It is important to state that, pursuant to Article 2-sexies, paragraph 1, of the current decree, the provisions allowing the processing of such special categories of personal data may be established, in the internal legal system, by primary or secondary sources of law.

4.7 Summary

Sweden has no explicit mention of research and archival purposes as a specific public interest for the processing of special categories of personal data. However, processing of personal data for research purposes must be in accordance with the Ethical Review Act⁵⁹. In summary, the terms, and conditions for processing special categories of personal data vary from one country to another. However, the common denominator is that processing for scientific, historical, and archival purposes is legitimate given that adequate safeguards⁶⁰. This is not surprising, seeing that Art. 9.2 (j) explicitly refers directly to this article. It is also worth mentioning that the Italian and Danish legislators seem to demand a “significant” public interest, which might indicate a higher threshold using Art. 9.2 (j) as a legal ground.

TABLE 2 A SUMMARY OF HOW LAWFUL PROCESSING OF SPECIAL (SENSITIVE) CATEGORIES OF PERSONAL DATA FOR ARCHIVAL PURPOSES IN THE PUBLIC INTEREST AND FOR RESEARCH PURPOSES, ARTICLE 9.2 (J) IS INTERPRETED IN SWEDEN, FINLAND, DENMARK, NORWAY, GERMANY, AND ITALY.

The processing of special (sensitive) categories of personal data		
	Research	Archive
Sweden	The Ethical Review Act, §§ 3 and 6. Also §§ 7- 11 a. <i>Ethical approval must be granted. Approval depends on the requirements for lawful processing of special categories of personal data, which, amongst other things, entails attest of necessity and proportionality.</i>	In the Data protection Act, Chapter 3, § 6. <i>When necessary, in order to follow regulations on the conservation and care of archives. The government can make regulations allowing others to process for archival purposes in the public interest.</i>

⁵⁹ See § 3, https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2003460-om-etikprovnig-av-forskning-som_sfs-2003-460 [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁶⁰ See GDPR art. 89.1, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-89-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

Finland	The Data protection Act, § 6 (7). <i>May be processed for scientific/historical research or statistics. Demands necessary safeguards after § 6(2) number 1-11.</i>	The Data protection Act, § 6 (8). <i>May be processed for archival purposes in the public interest (except from genetic data). Demands necessary safeguards after § 6(2) number 1-11.</i>
Denmark	The Data Protection Act, §10, and Bekendtgørelse, nr 1509 af 18/12/2019 <i>Lawful processing, if necessary, for historical/scientific investigations of significant importance for society. If specific demands in the mentioned "Bekendtgørelse" are met, it is not necessary to gather approval from the supervision authority.</i>	Regulated in archive laws.
Norway	The Data protection Act, § 9. <i>May be processed for historical/scientific research and statistics in the public interest if proportionate, necessary, appropriate safeguards are met and consulted a DPO or performed a DPIA.</i>	The Data protection Act, § 9. <i>May be processed for historical/scientific research and statistics in the public interest if proportionate, necessary, appropriate safeguards are met and consulted a DPO or performed a DPIA.</i>
Germany	The BDSG section 27 (1). <i>Lawful processing for scientific or historical research purposes or statistics purposes, if proportionate and necessary. Necessary measures must be taken (see Table 3).</i>	The BDSG section 28. <i>Lawful for archive purposes in the public interest. Necessary measures must be taken (see Table 3).</i>
Italy	<i>Processing might be lawful if specific conditions are met and a significant public interest. Provisions allowing the processing may be established in the internal legal system, by primary or secondary sources of law.</i>	<i>No supplementary provisions.</i>

5 Appropriate safeguards pursuant to GDPR

Article 89.1

As mentioned previously in this deliverable, the processing of personal data may only take place on the condition that the safeguards of the Regulation are respected. To fulfil this prerequisite, the Regulation issues several provisions ensuring the lawful processing of data, for example, the principle of clarity, proportionality and necessity stated in Article 5 and Article 6. Other important aspects of ensuring the lawful processing of data are the provisions issued in Articles 24, 32 and 89. Together, these provisions make up a framework for ensuring the rights and freedoms of the data subject, with Article 89.1 being the most important provision regarding the processing of personal data for research purposes.

Article 89 is a new provision, in the sense that it has no equivalent in the 1995 Directive⁶¹.

Article 89.1 states that “processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this Regulation, for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organizational measures are in place in particular in order to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.”⁶²

According to Article 89.1, technical and organizational measures can include anonymization as the preferred safeguard, with pseudonymisation being the alternative solution. However, the preamble item 156⁶³ suggests that the safeguards pursuant to Article 89.1 are not exhaustive, and it is assumed that the Union parties should issue national provisions (introduce supplementary safeguards to protect personal data) to ensure safeguards. This perception is supported when reading GDPR Article 9.2 (j) which determines that the “[...] member State law [...] shall ... provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and interests of the data subject”⁶⁴, with reference to the demands of Article 89.1.

⁶¹ Eurlex, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31995L0046&rid=5> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁶² GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-89-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁶³ Eurlex, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁶⁴ GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

The following paragraphs will provide an overview as to how the selected countries used the scope introduced in this paragraph, and how this is implemented in national law before we discuss the implications with regard to scientific research. Table 3 presents a summary of how they have chosen to interpret the requirement for these “appropriate safeguards” and “suitable and specific measures”. To receive special categories of personal data from EOSC, the researchers therefore must make appropriate safeguards. Which safeguards must be made, depends on the national supplementary legislation.

5.1 Sweden

There is no mentioning in the Swedish Personal Data Act addressing what is deemed appropriate as safeguards. When it comes to the processing of personal data for research purposes, researchers need an ethical⁶⁵. Apart from this, there are no specific safeguards stated. Other Swedish special laws that are outside the scope of this study, may state suitable safeguards for processing of special categories of personal data, for research and archiving purposes.

5.2 Finland

The Data protection Act of Finland⁶⁶, §§ 6 (7) and 6 (8) states that special categories of personal data may be processed for scientific/historical research or statistics, and archival purposes in the public interest (except from genetic data) if specific and suitable measures. The measures are:

1. Measures to being able to demonstrate who has registered, changed, or disclosed personal data
2. Measures to heighten the competence of personnel processing personal data
3. Appointment of a DPO
4. The controller and processors internal measures to prevent the proliferation of personal data
5. Pseudonymisation
6. Encryption
7. Measures to continuously ensure the confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of the processing systems and services relating to the processing of personal data, including the ability to restore availability and access to the data in a reasonable time in a physical or technical incident. A procedure for periodically testing, investigating, and evaluating the effectiveness of the technical and organizational measures to ensure the safety of the treatment,

⁶⁵ See Act on Ethical Review, available here: https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2003460-om-etikproving-av-forskning-som_sfs-2003-460 [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁶⁶ Finlex.fi, <https://www.finlex.fi/sv/laki/alkup/2018/20181050> [accessed 23.06.2021]

8. Special procedural rules to ensure that data protection and this law are observed when personal data is transferred or processed for any other purpose,
9. Carrying out an impact assessment on data protection pursuant to article 35 of the regulation
10. Other technical, procedural, and organizational measures.

5.3 Denmark

The Danish Personal Data Act has no specific reference to what should be considered as “appropriate safeguards” as stated in Article 89.1. However, both the Controller and receiver are obliged to make some necessary safety measures⁶⁷ which will be presented in the following. If these demands are not met, the sharing must be approved by the Danish supervision authority.

First, the Controller can only share data in a pseudonymised manner⁶⁸. However, if necessary, for the relevant statistical or scientific purpose, identifiable data might be given (but the receiver must use a scrambling key). If the sharing of data takes place online, the receiver must make appropriate safety measures. If special categories of personal data, this means at least encryption, cf. § 6. In order to reach the needed level of security proportional to the relevant level of risk, relevant technical and organizational measures must be taken in accordance with the GDPR Article 32, cf. §. 7.

The receiver must be authorized by the Controller. Persons getting access to the data, must be given instructions for the processing (derby not to process data for other purposes than statistical or scientific investigations). In order to reach the needed level of security proportional to the relevant level of risk, relevant technical and organizational measures must be taken in accordance with the GDPR Article 32⁶⁹. At the end of the statistical or scientific investigation, personal data shall be deleted, be anonymized, get destroyed or be returned to the Controller. The data may also get transferred to archives in correspondence with archive regulations.

5.4 Norway

The Norwegian Personal Data Act reiterates the duty to ensure “appropriate safeguards” in accordance with Article 89.1 in several provisions, hereunder §§ 8 and 9⁷⁰. In the motives, the Ministry of Justice states

⁶⁷ These are regulated in § 3 following in the Executive order (“Bekentgørelse”), <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁶⁸ See § 3, See § 14, <http://www.socialjura.dk/content-storage/regler/2019/bek-1509-af-1812-2019/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁶⁹ GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-32-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁷⁰ Lovdata.no, <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

that neither the regulation itself, nor the preamble, provides clear guidance on the content of the requirements for safeguards, or for “suitable and specific measures”, other than entailing anonymization and/or pseudonymisation and provisions to ensure confidentiality. The Ministry assumes that the assessment of these safeguards/measures must be based on the duty to ensure that the processing is in accordance with the principles of article 5 and considering the sensitivity of the data and the risk associated with the processing, amongst other things. Other safeguards/measures might be prior consultation of the supervisory authority or a DPO.

As mentioned previously, the DPO's main task is to inform and advise on the obligations of the Controller set in GDPR. The DPO shall, upon request, provide advice on the DPIA and monitor the implementation of the impact assessments. It is, however, the Controller, who is responsible for ensuring that such assessments are carried out. Though, the DPO can play an important role in assisting the person responsible for processing in these assessments.

5.5 Germany

BDSG Section 22 (2) states that when processing special categories of personal data, without consent, appropriate and specific measures shall be taken to safeguard the interests of the data subject. Considering the state of the art, the cost of implementation and the nature, scope, context, and purposes of processing as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for rights and freedoms of natural persons posed by the processing, these measures may include the following:

1. Technical organizational measures to ensure that processing complies with GDPR
2. Measures to ensure that it is subsequently possible to verify and establish whether and by whom personal data were input, altered or removed
3. Measures to increase awareness of staff involved in processing operations
4. Designation of a DPO
5. Restrictions on access to personal data within the controller and by processors
6. The pseudonymisation of personal data
7. The encryption of personal data
8. Measures to ensure the ability, confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of processing systems and services related to the processing of personal data, including the ability to rapidly restore availability and access in the event of a physical or technical incident
9. A process for regularly testing, assessing, and evaluating the effectiveness of technical and organizational measures for ensuring the security of the processing
10. Specific rules of procedure to ensure compliance with this Act and with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 in the event of transfer or processing for other purposes.

In addition, when processing special categories of personal data (without consent) for research purposes, data shall be anonymized as soon as the research purpose is fulfilled, unless this conflicts with legitimate interest of the data subject. Before de-identification, the data controller must separately store the

characteristics enabling information to be associated with an identified or identifiable individual. The data controller may combine information only if required to fulfil the processing purpose⁷¹.

5.6 Italy

Regarding processing of special categories of personal data (e.g., biometric, genetic and health data), the Guarantee will issue provisions on safeguard measures every two years, to identify security measures (e.g., cryptography and pseudonymisation procedures, minimisation measures, specific methods of selective data access) to provide information to data subjects to guarantee the data subjects' rights⁷².

It is the task team's understanding that no such provisions are yet given by the Italian legislator. Article 89.1 therefore applies directly with no supplementary requirements regarding safeguards measures.

The mentioned provision will apply when processing biometric, genetic and health data. It remains to see if these safeguard measures also might be transferable when processing special categories of personal data in general.

5.7 Summary

Some of the countries, such as Finland, Denmark, and Germany, have made comprehensive lists of what are specific and suitable measures. It is the project groups understanding that also the Italian legislator soon will present a list of appropriate safeguard measures when processing biometric, genetic and health data. Norway on the other hand presupposes that safeguards are individually assessed by the controller for each processing. Sweden sees an ethical review as a suitable measure. Even though not all national supplementary legislations have regulated specific situations when the DPO is to be consulted (as in Norway), it is worth noting that the arrangements with a DPO is generally regulated in GDPR and will therefore apply in all EU/EEA countries.

This indicates that solutions to assessing specific safeguards pursuant to GDPR Article 89. 1⁷³ are quite varied. A common understanding as to what measures will satisfy the requirement of appropriate measures ("suitable, specific, technical, organizational") pursuant to Articles 89.1 and 9.2 (j), would make sharing of research data across borders easier.

⁷¹ See Section 27 (3) in BSGD, <https://dsgvo-gesetz.de/bdsg/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁷² Please note that all Italian legal sources are based on oral communication and non-English versions, and that the legal situation might not be correctly presented in this report. These issues can be further explored in task 8.3 Legal and Ethical issues.

⁷³ GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-89-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

TABLE 3 A SUMMARY OF HOW THE COUNTRIES IN THIS DELIVERABLE INTERPRET THE REQUIREMENT FOR THE “APPROPRIATE SAFEGUARDS” AND “SUITABLE AND SPECIFIC MEASURES”.

Protecting the rights and freedoms of the data subjects when processing personal data for research purposes by considering appropriate safeguards pursuant to Article 89 (1).		
	Research	Archive
Sweden	<p>The Data Protection Act.</p> <p><i>No explicit regulation.</i></p> <p>The Ethical Review Act, §§ 7 – 11a.</p> <p><i>Constitutes the requirements for lawful processing of special categories of personal data.</i></p> <p><i>Ethical approval considered as constituting a “suitable and specific measure”.</i></p>	<p>The Data Protection act.</p> <p><i>No explicit regulation.</i></p>
Finland	<p>The Data protection Act, § 6 (2) number 1-11, cf. § 6 (1) number 7.</p> <p><i>Eleven explicit measures named in § 6 (2), 1-11.</i></p>	<p>The Data protection Act, § 6 (2) number 1-11, cf. § 6 (1) number 8.</p> <p><i>Eleven explicit measures named in § 6 (2), 1-11.</i></p>
Denmark	<p>The Data Protection Act.</p> <p><i>No explicit regulation.</i></p> <p>The Executive order (“Bekendtgørelse”, nr 1509 af 18/12/2019). <i>The Controller and receiver are obliged to make some necessary safety measures. If these demands are not met, sharing must be approved by the Danish supervision authority.</i></p>	<p>Regulated in archive laws.</p>
Norway	<p>The Data Protection Act, §§ 8 and 9.</p> <p><i>Processing must be in accordance with Article 89.1. Concrete assessment in each case considering the principles in Article 5. Researcher must consult with a DPO or performer a DPIA before processing special categories of personal data.</i></p>	<p>The Data Protection Act, §§ 8 and 9.</p> <p><i>Processing must be in accordance with Article 89.1. Concrete assessment in each case considering the principles in Article 5. Researcher must consult with a DPO or performer a DPIA before processing special categories of personal data.</i></p>

Germany	<p>The BDSG Section 22 (2) and Section 27(3).</p> <p><i>Eleven explicit measures named in Section 22 (2). Necessary measures depend on a concrete assessment in each case.</i></p> <p><i>Main rule to anonymize special categories of personal data when research purpose fulfilled, unless in conflict with interests of the data subject.</i></p>	<p>The BDSG Section 22 (2).</p> <p><i>Eleven explicit measures named in Section 22 (2). Necessary measures depend on a concrete assessment in each case.</i></p>
Italy	<p>No explicit regulation yet. However, every second year it shall be given provisions on appropriate safeguards measures for processing biometric, genetic and health data.</p>	<p>No explicit regulation.</p>

6 Processing personal data relating to criminal conviction and offences

The GDPR rules for special categories of personal data in GDPR Article 9⁷⁴ does not include data about criminal allegations, proceedings, or convictions. Instead, GDPR Article 10 addresses the following:

“Processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, or related security measures based on Article 6(1) shall be carried out only under the control of official authority or when the processing is authorised by Union or Member State law providing for appropriate safeguards for the rights and freedoms of data subjects. Any comprehensive register of criminal convictions shall be kept only under the control of official authority.”⁷⁵

Therefore, according to the Regulation, supplementary legislation is required for national laws to allow the possibility of the processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences by others than official authorities.

As mentioned previously, sharing of such data can take place between countries with equivalent protection and this to researchers placed in a country where supplementary national legislation has been given. This also means that if data related to criminal convictions and offences are included in EOSC, this will have implications for the accessibility of these data. Table 4 summarises how/if the selected countries have given supplementary provisions for processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences.

6.1 Sweden

The Swedish General Data Protection Act chapter 3, § 8⁷⁶ determines that personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, can only be processed by an official authority. However, exceptions can be made if the processing is necessary to obey provisions about archive.

⁷⁴ GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁷⁵ GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-10-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁷⁶ Riksdagen.se, https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2018218-med-kompletterande-bestammelser_sfs-2018-218 [accessed 23.06.2021]

In § 9⁷⁷ it is stated that the government may issue provisions deciding in what instances other controllers/processors beside official authorities may process personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences.

The Ethical Review Act § 3 (2)⁷⁸ states that the act also applies to research entailing processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences. The Ethical review applies regardless of whether the processing is carried out by public authorities, or not.

Approval according to the Ethical Review Act⁷⁹ constitutes a legal basis for processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences for research purposes. The Ethical Review Act §3 (2) states that this law shall apply to research that includes the handling of personal data regarding violations of law that include crimes, judgments in criminal cases, penal law sanctions, or administrative deprivation of liberty, as defined in Section 21 of the Personal Data Act⁸⁰. This research may only be conducted if it has been approved subsequent to an ethical vetting. As for special categories of personal data, §§ 7-11a⁸¹ constitutes the requirements for lawful processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences, which, amongst other things, entails attest of necessity and proportionality.

6.2 Finland

The Data protection Act of Finland⁸², § 7.2 states that personal data subject to Article 10 may be processed for research purposes, if the obligations mentioned in § 6 second paragraph are met⁸³.

⁷⁷ Riksdagen.se, https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2018218-med-kompletterande-bestammelser_sfs-2018-218 [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁷⁸ Riksdagen.se, https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2003460-om-etikprovning-av-forskning-som_sfs-2003-460 [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁷⁹ See §§ 3 (2) and 6, https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2003460-om-etikprovning-av-forskning-som_sfs-2003-460 [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸⁰ Riksdagen.se, https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2018218-med-kompletterande-bestammelser_sfs-2018-218 [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸¹ Riksdagen.se, https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/lag-2018218-med-kompletterande-bestammelser_sfs-2018-218 [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸² Finlex.fi, <https://www.finlex.fi/sv/laki/alkup/2018/20181050> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸³ See also combined with § 6 (1) number 7, <https://www.finlex.fi/sv/laki/alkup/2018/20181050> [accessed 23.06.2021]

There is no specific reference to § 6 (1) nr. 8 (archiving of research material in the public interest)⁸⁴. Still, processing for archival purposes can be lawful by the reference to § 6 /1), nr. 2⁸⁵, which allows processing for performing a task governed by law.

6.3 Denmark

The Danish Personal Data Act states in § 10 (1)⁸⁶ that information as mentioned in GDPR Article 9⁸⁷ and 10⁸⁸ can be processed if this is done solely in order to conduct statistical or scientific studies of significant societal importance and if processing is necessary for the sake of carrying out investigations. Information may only be disclosed to third parties after prior authorization from a public authority. The authority may set further terms for the disclosure.

6.4 Norway

The Personal Data Act⁸⁹ determines the need for a separate legal basis for research on personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences, and states in the motives that there is in principle no good reason as to why these categories of personal data should be treated differently. The Personal data Act § 11⁹⁰ therefore allows processing of these types of personal data for research purposes. Furthermore, the conditions of § 9 and 10⁹¹ apply the same way. The ministry emphasizes that § 11⁹² is not a legal basis for processing of criminal offences-data. The controller must instead exhibit that the processing is lawful according to Article 6.1(e)⁹³ and a supplementary legal basis in Union/Member State law must be fulfilled (in Norway's case, § 8)⁹⁴.

⁸⁴ Finlex.fi: <https://www.finlex.fi/sv/laki/alkup/2018/20181050> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸⁵ Finlex.fi: <https://www.finlex.fi/sv/laki/alkup/2018/20181050> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸⁶ Retsinformation.dk: <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/ta/2018/502> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸⁷ GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-9-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸⁸ GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-10-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁸⁹ Lovdata.no, <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁹⁰ Lovdata.no, <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁹¹ Lovdata.no, <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁹² Lovdata.no, <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁹³ GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/> [accessed 23.06.2021]

⁹⁴ Lovdata.no, <https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2018-06-15-38> [accessed 23.06.2021]

6.5 Germany

The BDSG⁹⁵ does not contain a provision authorizing processing data about criminal convictions and offenses. However, other German laws that are outside the scope of this deliverable may authorize processing this type of data. German law only permits public authorities to process this type of data.

6.6 Italy

It is the understanding of the task team that the Italian legislator has not given an explicit provision authorizing processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences⁹⁶. It is a national responsibility to regulate criminal matters, with regulations that are effective, proportionate, and dissuasive. In this perspective, the Italian legislator has reviewed the criminal cases according to the Code regarding the protection of personal data, substantially confirming them, introducing the forecast of the damage as a characterizing element as an alternative to the profit purpose. Therefore, it is not held against the sole economic profit of the perpetrator of the offense but also of the damage caused to the interested parties, including the damage of the image and the reputation of the victim. To limit the risk of overlaps between the administrative and criminal proceedings, a coordination mechanism has been inserted which provides that the Public Ministry informs the Control Authority immediately. In the same way, the Guarantor will be registered with the Public Ministry of the documentation collected in the administrative seat if a crime is presumed to exist.

6.7 Summary

Norway, Sweden, Denmark, and Finland have a general provision relating to criminal convictions and offences which applies to research. Some countries require ethical review regardless of whether the processor is a public authority or not, e.g., in Sweden, the Ethical Review Act requires that research on categories of personal data listed in Article 9.1 GDPR as well as criminal convictions and offenses must be approved by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority. Accordingly, the Ethical Review Act provides the legally based safeguard required for research. The project team could not find any provision authorizing processing these kinds of data in the German laws. Furthermore, it is our understanding that the Italian legislator has not given an explicit provision authorizing processing of personal data related to criminal

⁹⁵ <https://dsgvo-gesetz.de/bdsg/> [accessed 26.06.2021]

⁹⁶ Note that all Italian legal sources are based on oral communication and non-English versions, and that the legal situation might not be correctly presented in this report. These issues can be further explored in task 8.3 Legal and Ethical issues.

convictions and offences. As mentioned in section 6.1 in this deliverable, supplementary legislation is required in order for national laws to allow the possibility of the processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences by others than official authorities. Therefore, sharing data across borders might be an issue, if a receiver is subject to a nation without national regulation permitting processing of criminal convictions or offences.

TABLE 4 A SUMMARY OF HOW THE DIFFERENT COUNTRIES INTERPRET PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA RELATING TO CRIMINAL CONVICTIONS AND OFFENCES, CF. ARTICLE 10.

Processing of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences		
	Research	Archive
Sweden	<p>The Ethical Review Act, §§ 3 (2) and 6. Also §§ 7- 11a.</p> <p><i>Ethical approval must be granted. Approval depends on the requirements for lawful processing of data relating to criminal convictions and offences, which, amongst other things, entails attest of necessity and proportionality.</i></p>	<p>The Data Protection Act, Chapter 3, § 8.</p> <p><i>Others than authorities may process if necessary to obey archive provisions.</i></p>
Finland	<p>The Data protection Act, § 7 (2), cf. § 6 (1) number 7.</p> <p><i>May be processed for research purpose if obligations mentioned in § 6 (2) number 1-11 are met.</i></p>	<p>The Data protection Act.</p> <p><i>No explicit regulation. Perhaps allowed by § 7(2), cf. § 6 (1) number 2 if archiving is a task governed by law.</i></p>
Denmark	<p>The Personal Data Protection Act, § 10.</p> <p><i>Lawful processing if solely conducting statistical or scientific studies of significant social importance, and necessary to carry out investigations. Disclosing to third parties demands authorization from public authority.</i></p>	<p>Regulated in archive laws.</p>
Norway	<p>The Personal Data Protection Act, § 11.</p> <p>Lawful processing for research purposes. Processing must be lawful according to Article 6.1 e) and the personal data protection act § 8. Condition in § 9 must be met.</p>	<p>The Personal Data Protection Act, § 11.</p> <p>Lawful processing for archiving purposes, Processing must be lawful according to Article 6.1 e) and the data protection act § 8. Condition in § 9 must be met.</p>

Germany	No explicit regulation in the BDSG.	No explicit regulation in the BDSG.
Italy	No explicit regulation.	No explicit regulation.

7 European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

7.1 What is EOSC and its purpose?

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is an initiative by the European Commission (EC) to foster better collaboration between researchers, and science and technology professionals. According to the EOSC website EOSC is managed by the 12-member Executive Board, a body of representatives from the research and e-infrastructures communities, all appointed by the EC. All Executive Board members are appointed in a personal capacity and represent Pan-European organizations of relevant for the EOSC implementation⁹⁷.

The EOSC brings together institutional, national, and European stakeholders, initiatives, and data infrastructures to develop an inclusive open science ecosystem in Europe. It aims to develop a trusted, virtual, federated environment that cuts across borders and scientific disciplines to store, share, process, and re-use research digital objects (like publications, data, and software) following FAIR principles⁹⁸.

The European Commission set three goals for research and innovation policy within European Union: Open Innovation, Open Science and Open to the World⁹⁹.

The main goal of Open science is to encourage European research and innovation systems to move towards a reality where knowledge is created through international and global collaborations. The premise behind Open science is to extend the principles of openness to the whole research cycle, and thereby allowing knowledge to circulate more freely to promote sharing and collaboration as early as possible. This will, among other things, promote best practices of global data findability and accessibility, and allow easier replicability of results and limit data wastage. The outcome of Open science would entail a change to the way science and research is done.

⁹⁷ EOSCsecretariat.eu EOSC Executive Board: www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-governance/eosc-executive-board [accessed 26.05.2021]

⁹⁸ European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

What the cloud is, how it relates to other strategies, how it was developed and what will happen in the future: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science/eosc_en [accessed 26.05.2021]

⁹⁹ European Commission website, https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/past-research-and-innovation-policy-goals_en [accessed 26.05.2021]

The concepts discussed above are not new, and it has been postulated that in the long term, the adjective Open will be redundant, as science will be open by default, and it would solely be named Science.

7.2 The GDPRs implications for EOSC – a judicial perspective

So far, the focus of this deliverable has been to name specific legal grounds for processing personal data that are most relevant to research. It is plausible to think that such legal grounds will only be relevant when gathering research data, for instance during fieldwork. However, the GDPR art. 4.2 determines that also sharing, storing and archiving of personal data is seen as a processing of personal data and will also need a legal ground.

Therefore, the ability for EOSC to receive personal data might depend on possible legal grounds in the Member States, where the responsible controllers are placed. As mentioned, the GDPR allows Member States to give supplementary legislation. The assessment on how the different countries have taken advantage of this possibility, has shown that as a result, the terms for applying legal grounds (due to national supplementary legislation), might vary from one state to another.

As all processing of personal data must have a legal ground, the different interpretations and supplementations in national legislations might also affect the possibility of users of EOSC. That is, if national legislator has not granted a supplementary provision in national law, researchers in that country will not have a legal ground for processing (receiving) the data from EOSC. When organizing EOSC, a plan for who will assess if receivers have sufficient legal ground for receiving data should be made. Among other thing, it should be stressed what documentation must be made from researchers when requesting data from EOSC.

As mentioned in the beginning of this deliverable, consent is one of the most applicable legal grounds when processing personal data in research projects. The terms for a valid consent as legal ground is regulated in GDPR and the GDPR does not leave room for national supplementary on this matter. Therefore, it seems plausible that if using consent as legal ground, this will not have implications for EOSC as this will be applicable for all Member States. However, the wording in the consent given from the data subject to the researcher might cause hinders for sharing data with others, including through EOSC. For instance, the consent might state that data are to be deleted at project end and until that date only be processed by the project group for one specific research purpose. In such a case, the consent does not grant sharing of data and will have implications for EOSC, as others will be hindered to process (receiving, storing etc.) the data.

However, a significant part of the total amount of research conducted each year is performed without consent from data subjects (participants), because consensual processing is impossible or disproportionately difficult. Thus, as mentioned, there is a need for a national supplementary that substitutes processing based on consent. Most of the countries examined in this deliverable have implemented national provisions that are beneficial for research and archival purposes, except for the processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences. However, as mentioned, the terms for applying such legal grounds may vary and will therefore differ from one country to another. When organizing EOSC, a plan should be made for who will assess if these terms are fulfilled in each case, to make sure all parties processing the data have a legal ground.

One of the main principles of the GDPR is transparency, cf. Art. 5. To process data in a transparent manner it is important that the data subjects are informed about how their data are being processed. Information is also an ethical requirement for most research and must be considered and implemented throughout the research lifecycle, from planning to publication to sharing. This applies regardless of which legal ground is being used. If researchers have not informed the participants of their plans to share data, it will be considered a breach of the principle of transparency if doing it anyway. The information provided to data subjects, might therefore have implications for EOSC, as data should be processed as informed – and as such, in a transparent manner. This implication will be minimized if researchers can give the data subjects new information, prior to sharing their data. However, if the legal basis is consent it can be argued that the previous consent will not include such sharing and therefore a new consent must be documented after being presented with such new information.

As mentioned previously, the GDPR allows member states to regulate which safety measures are required when using public interest/scientific research as legal ground for processing of personal data. As the deliverable shows, the required safety measures differ from one country to another. As those requirements differ from one country to another, this might have implications for EOSC, depending on if EOSC decides to assess such documentation. When organizing EOSC, a plan should be made for who will assess if receivers have sufficient safety measures in place for receiving data, and which measures to secure the data at EOSC, if using public interest/scientific research/archiving purposed as the legal ground. Among other thing, it should be stressed what documentation on planned measures must be made by the researchers when requesting data from EOSC.

8 Insight into researchers' experience

This section of the deliverable will present findings from interviews with 14 researchers, from three different European countries (Denmark, Italy, and Norway). The point of view of researchers is, important to examine the main impacts of the GDPR on the daily life of the research environment. The researchers were asked the following questions (section 14 Interview guide):

- Has the research process changed due to GDPR?
 - Can you access the same data?
 - Can you store the same data?
 - Can you share your data with relevant colleagues?
- Have you tried applying for research funds after the GDPR?
 - If so, how was it as compared to before?
 - If not, do you have colleagues who tried, and what was their experience?
- Have you tried applying for research funds after the GDPR?
 - If so, how was it as compared to before?
 - If not, do you have colleagues who tried, and what was their experience?
 - Have the implementation of DPO affected the research process?

Several different aspects can influence how researchers in different countries have experienced the impact of the GDPR; such as how data protection was regulated prior to the GDPR and their specific field of research. For instance, Norway has had a rather strict data protection law also prior the GDPR and has an extensive experience with the use of a DPO in the field of research. These are all factors that might affect how researchers experience the impacts of the European Data Protection Law.

Further, it is also important to stress that findings from these interviews cannot be generalised to represent the experience of the research environment in general. Instead, it represents the experiences of a few selected researchers.

8.1 Changes in the research process

The researchers were first asked a general question about how the GDPR had affected the research process, with regards to accessing data, sharing, and storing data. The results are summarised in Table 5.

8.1.1 Denmark

Four health and medical researchers were interviewed in February 2020. In Denmark, medical research can be affiliated on different levels. Universities are affiliated to the university hospitals, whereas there are five regions in Denmark responsible for all the other hospitals. Due to this setup, three of the researchers described collaborating with units outside the region or a university hospital as extremely difficult after the GDPR. All the regions hired legal support to make sure they were GDPR compliant, but there was no overall coordination between the regions, which resulted in all five regions interpreting the

GDPR differently. This means that conducting research after the implementation of the GDPR has clearly become more difficult if researchers include data/patients from other regions or other systems than their own. There are no clear procedures, and the legal departments are very strict in their assessments. Some collaborations between hospital units have simply been shut down, because it is not worth the effort of paperwork/emails. Researchers get the overall impression that the legal departments are afraid of the fines, and work under the motto: Better safe than sorry. It is also impossible to get a genuine answer from the legal departments. Often, they can give a vague answer on the phone but nothing via email. This makes it extremely difficult for some of the researchers. The overall impression is that the legal officers do not have experience with research data and the need for personal data in order to conduct health research. A legal officer had suggested “to delete all cohorts, due to the fact that they contained personal data”. Therefore, there is a huge gap between the legal departments and the research departments in Denmark.

8.1.2 Norway

Two health and medical researchers, one social media researcher, and one social anthropology researcher, were interviewed from February to September 2020. One of the researchers from the health sector emphasized that a major difference is that the process to get access to research data (especially quantitative health data) has been prolonged after the implementation of the GDPR. This is especially the case if different data sets need to be merged or linked.

According to the researcher, one of the explanations for this prolonged process might be that the DPOs employed by the data owners are judicial experts and not familiar with the context of research data. They lack training in making these kinds of assessments and they lack knowledge of research data. In addition, the fines they might receive, if they were to make the wrong assessment, make them even more careful. In time, once the DPOs grow more accustomed to the possibilities and limits of the GDPR and to the context of research data, this will hopefully improve.

According to another researcher, who has a background in social media research, there has not been major challenges after the implementation of the GDPR. However, the social media researcher points out that it has become more challenging to get access to Facebook data now than previously. Facebook will only share data with researchers that are made public and will not share comments that contain names of private persons. However, since the researchers do get access to the Facebook posts, their links/URLs, shares and likes, they can access the comment sections of the posts if it is necessary for their research purpose. Before the implementation of the GDPR researchers could get access to both the posts and the comments sections on Facebook. The researcher specifies that this has both negative and positive implications, depending on the purpose and focus of the research. As for other social media sites, such as Twitter, Instagram and blogs, there have been no restrictions on or changes to what data the researcher can access since the GDPR came into force.

According to the researcher with a background in social anthropology, the collection of data has not changed. Many of the researchers in this field collect data in countries outside the EU. In order to do research in these countries one needs permission from local research ethics councils. This includes the processing of data, as well as an ethical assessment. In addition, researchers must be employed at reputable institutions in order to get permission to do research. This process has not changed after the implementation of the GDPR. However, it is important for anthropology departments to be aware of institutional changes related the GDPR, especially as the ethics and data requirements have real

consequences for the epistemology of anthropological research. The rationale of conducting activities such as ‘hanging out’, ‘chatting with folks’, ‘roaming the field’ now carries the extra weight of formalized review and data protection, as well as legal grounds, which affects the ways in which anthropologists are required to do research.

It is pointed out by one of the researchers that there are no difficulties sharing data inside Europe, but once you need to share personal data with researchers outside Europe, for instance in the United States or with partners in Russia, it becomes more challenging.

8.1.3 Italy

All the Italian researchers described the impact of the GDPR as being marginal, although one medical researcher pointed out that data management needs to be documented prior to processing of data.

The history of science researcher has noticed a slowdown in the internal organizational procedures for teaching students. A burdening of the procedures for carrying out laboratory activities was noted, especially regarding didactic activity in museums and archives.

TABLE 5 A SUMMARY OF HOW THE GDPR HAD AFFECTED THE RESEARCH PROCESS, WITH REGARD TO ACCESSING DATA, SHARING AND STORING DATA IN NORWAY, DENMARK, AND ITALY.

Has the research process changed due to GDPR?			
Researcher's residence	Research field	Yes/No/Don't know	If yes, what is different?
Norway	Health research	Yes	The duration of receiving research data is longer.
Norway	Social media researcher	Yes	Some social media sites share less data then earlier.
Norway	Health research	Don't know	
Norway	Social anthropology Research	Don't know	
Denmark	Health Research	Yes	Collaborations are nearly impossible due to different levels and different interpretations of GDPR.
Denmark	Health Research	Yes	Collaborations across regions are not possible in the same way. Legal officers often don't understand research issues and the need for personal data
Denmark	Health Research	Yes	Research process nearly stopped because the legal officers are too slow and not willing to give clear answers.
Denmark	Health Research	Yes	More legal process, longer waiting time for legal officers to respond to issues.

Italy	History Philosophy Social Sciences research	Yes	Requirement to obtain extra educational qualifications
Italy	History of science	Yes	In order to do research on teaching statistics, it is necessary to request authorization from the participants of laboratories / sessions for data processing.
Italy	Health research	Yes	Necessary to fill out forms before the collection of user data
Italy	Archaeology	No	

8.2 Changes in applying for research funds

All the researchers were asked whether there have been changes to the process of applying for research funds. The results are described in the sections below. A summary is presented in Table 6.

8.2.1 Denmark

Researchers from Denmark had not noticed any significant changes in applying for research funds. One researcher had given up on applying for funds from a French hospital unit due to the legal setup. However, the overall impression was that the GDPR just added more paper to the contract. One mentioned: “Often I give up, I just accept the changes the legal department adds to the contract”.

8.2.2 Norway

One of the researchers stated that the application process for research funding after the implementation of the GDPR has become more comprehensive and elaborate, with a greater focus on the part that involves ethics and personal data. Two of the researchers pointed out that the GDPR has affected the way research projects are organized. For instance, one of the researchers is involved in a large European research project that has changed the way data is analysed and gathered in order to avoid the rules on transferring personal data in Chapter 5 of the GDPR¹⁰⁰. It is too early to say whether this will affect the methods used for analysing data.

¹⁰⁰ GDPR: <https://gdpr-info.eu/chapter-5/> [accessed 26.05.2021]

8.2.3 Italy

None of the researchers interviewed in Italy had experienced any changes to the process of applying for research funds after the implementation of the GDPR.

TABLE 6 A SUMMARY OF HOW THE PROCESS OF APPLYING FOR RESEARCH FUNDS CHANGED IN THE VARIOUS COUNTRIES AFTER IMPLEMENTATION OF THE GDPR

Has the process of applying for research funds after the GDPR changed?			
Researcher´s residence	Research field	Yes/No/Don't know	If yes, what is different?
Norway	Health research	No	
Norway	Social media researcher	No	
Norway	Health research	No	
Norway	Social anthropology Research	Yes	More focus on ethics and personal data
Denmark	Health research	Yes	More paperwork. One project gave up beforehand.
Denmark	Health research	Yes	More paperwork
Denmark	Health research	Yes	More paperwork
Denmark	Health research	Yes	More paperwork
Italy	History Philosophy Social Sciences research	No	
Italy	History of science	No	
Italy	Health research	No	
Italy	Archaeology	No	

8.3 Changes to the publishing and/or archiving process?

All researchers were asked about the impact the GDPR has had on the process of publishing research results and archiving research data. The results are described in the following sections. A summary is presented in Table 7.

8.3.1 Denmark

None of the researchers interviewed had completed a research project and/or published material after the introduction of the GDPR. However, it should be noted that the archiving process in Denmark has not changed since it is mandatory to deliverable the ending of projects to the Danish National Archives, where it is decided whether the data should be archived. Rigsarkivet - The Danish National Archives

have legal rights to receive and store personal data. In addition, the Danish archives makes data accessible for research purposes.

8.3.2 Norway

One experience from the publishing process is that researchers have been asked to share sensitive personal data with scientific journals during the publishing process. However, this was not possible due to the privacy of the data subjects and the fact that data subjects had not given their consent for sharing data with journals. It is the impression of the researchers that this is an explanation that the journals accept, and that it is sufficient to receive an aggregated and anonymized data set.

The focus on data security and good solutions for storing research data securely has become a higher priority at universities after implementation of the GDPR. Although this has been sought after by researchers since before 2018, it has just recently gotten a bigger focus, most likely due to the GDPR. This has resulted in clearer guidelines from universities on safe solutions for storing various categories of research data. NSD – the Norwegian Centre for Research Data, is one of the largest archives for research data of its kind and provides data to researchers and students in Norway and abroad, equal to the Danish National Archives. Moreover, NSD is a resource center, which assists researchers regarding data gathering, data analysis, methodology, privacy, and research ethics. NSD archives and disseminates data for both national and international research communities and has one of the largest professional communities in Europe with competence in the field of personal data protection in research.

The researcher of the history of science noted that the processing of data for archiving purposes, for scientific or historical research purposes, or for statistical purposes, is subject to adequate guarantees for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. These guarantees ensure that technical and organizational measures have been put in place, to guarantee compliance with the principle of data minimization. In the research sector, one such measure is pseudonymisation, which means that the data subject can no longer be identified without the use of additional information.

TABLE 7 THE TABLE SHOWS A SUMMARY OF HOW THE GDPR HAS IMPACTED THE PROCESS OF PUBLISHING RESEARCH RESULTS AND ARCHIVING RESEARCH DATA IN NORWAY, DENMARK, AND ITALY.

Have the publishing and/or archiving process changed after the GDPR?	
Researcher´s residence	Yes/No/Don't know
Norway	No
Denmark	No
Italy	No

8.4 The assignment of a Data Protection Officer

With the implementation of the GDPR, it became mandatory for many organizations, universities and research institutions, to employ a DPO. The primary role of a DPO at a university or research institution

is to ensure that the organization processes personal data in compliance with data protection rules, e.g., by providing advice and recommendations to the institution regarding the interpretation or application of the data protection rules. The DPO is an advisor to the management, and data responsibility always lies with the management at the institution. A DPO is normally one individual but is often supported by a bigger judicial team or department. Table 8 shows how implementation of a DPO, from the interview subjects' point of view, has affected the research process in the various countries.

8.4.1 Denmark

In Denmark, the interviewed researchers had not been affected by the implementation of a DPO, but this is because they are often not in contact with the DPO but the legal department.

8.4.2 Norway

One of the researchers from the health sector pointed out that since the university appointed its own DPO every process has been prolonged. For instance, when a project requires a DPIA there are many different actors involved. This will probably improve, as the DPO gets more familiar with the University, research data and the law.

8.4.3 Italy

Parallel to the Norwegian situation, the interviewee in the medical research community noticed an increase in administrative requirements, as it is necessary to fill in various forms.

TABLE 8 A SUMMARY OF HOW IMPLEMENTATION OF A DPO HAS AFFECTED THE RESEARCH PROCESS IN THE VARIOUS COUNTRIES.

Has the implementation of DPO affected the research process?			
Researcher´s residence	Research field	Yes/No/Don't know	If yes, what is different?
Norway	Health research	Yes	The process is prolonged
Norway	Social media researcher	No	
Norway	Social anthropology Research	No	
Norway	Health research	No	
Denmark	Health research	No	
Denmark	Health research	No	
Denmark	Health research	No	
Denmark	Health research	No	
Italy	History Philosophy Social Sciences research	No	

Italy	History of science	No	
Italy	Health research	Yes	The process is prolonged
Italy	Archaeology	No	

9 The GDPRs implications for EOSC – from a general perspective

Sharing of data is a resourceful way to advance scientific research and to assure that the benefits derived from research data are utilized as widely as possible. After conducting interviews with researchers, some aspects on how the GDPR has affected the research environment, stands out. As EOSC is depending on engagement and will of the research environments to share their data, it is the project group's opinion that this aspect might have implications for EOSC. This differs from juridical implications mentioned above, that regulates the research environments possibility to share their data. This chapter illustrates some non-legal barriers, which in the project groups' opinion, might have implications for EOSC.

First, the fear of making mistakes in the field of privacy and receiving fees from Supervisory Authorities stands out. This has led to the involvement of juridical expertise without previous knowledge to research and the purpose and necessity of sharing research data in the research environment, both within and across borders. It seems like this has led to a strict interpretation of the GDPR and national safeguards. As mentioned, one of the rationales behind the GDPR has been to harmonize the legal framework for processing personal data in Europe and hence make it easier to share data across borders. This should make it easier for researchers across Europe to collaborate, stimulating progress in research. However, different and strict interpretations from judicial experts on how the law should be interpreted and different national supplementary provisions from its legislators make harmonization more challenging.

Accountability is one of the cornerstones of the GDPR. With the implementation of the GDPR all businesses and organisations processing personal data became responsible for being compliant with the GDPR and being able to demonstrate to the authorities that they are indeed compliant. The GDPR provides organisations with a set of tools to help demonstrate compliance, some of which are mandatory. One mandatory tool for many organisations is the employment of a DPO. Another tool, which is voluntary, is the creation of a sector specific Code of Conduct to demonstrate compliance.

For the research sector, this has resulted in the employment of DPOs and, in some countries, different legal teams to demonstrate compliance. If a research institute or a university fails to comply with the data protection rules, the consequences include suspension of activities and fines, and the latter especially has made many organisations become "over-compliant." The fines that can be imposed are substantial and many institutions therefore seem to follow the PR that it is "better to be safe than sorry."

This is demonstrated in Denmark, where it has become difficult to collaborate with researchers within different regions of the country even though the legal framework did not change. This could be a result of internal review, and procedural rules and regulation that are overcautious. Different regions and universities have hired legal support to demonstrate compliance, but there has not been an overall coordination between these regions. This means that carrying research since the implementation of the GDPR has become more challenging if researchers include data from other regions or other systems than their own. The result has been that some collaborations between hospital units have been shut down. Researchers have the overall impression that the legal departments are afraid of the fines, and that the legal officers do not know enough about research data and the need for personal data to conduct health research.

As a result, researchers, institutions, review boards, legal teams etc., are reluctant to share their research data, both in relation to other national institutions and abroad. This might have implications for EOSC, as researchers are afraid of the consequences of sharing the wrong data and therefore might not want to share their data to the infrastructure.

On the other hand, another aspect that stands out is the need of different approvals and actors, when wanting to receive data. This might have a positive implication to EOSC, due to positive engagement having one actor/infrastructure, which provides access to data. This might also adjust any implications related to the fear of sharing data as mentioned above. This engagement could also be made as an argument for having few actors within EOSC which will have mandate to provide researchers access to data, hindering possible prolonged processes as addressed by the interview objects.

Data sharing is an important part of research, and the foundation of scientific progress. Within many fields of research, pooled data on individuals are often needed to ensure the necessary size of the study population and to replicate or reproduce findings. In addition, data sharing encourages more connections and collaboration between scientists, which can result in improved decision-making. Scientists, utilizing previous work to build their research, can optimize achievement protocols and design experiments that complement previously obtained datasets. Access to data is essential for theoreticians attempting to provide a mechanistic explanation of observed phenomena. In addition, data availability is crucial for research transparency. Considerable challenges remain for data sharing outside of the EU/EEA. Particularly, there is a lack of mechanisms for transfer in non-consent-based research that can be used for sharing of personal data with research institutions in countries outside of the EU/EEA.

10 The UK and the GDPR - The UK being an "approved country" for the transfer of personal data

The UK left the EU on 31 January 2020 ("Brexit"). During the transition period to Brexit, there was no adequacy decision for the United Kingdom, although, the Brexit agreement between the United Kingdom and the EU provided a temporary provision for permission to transfer personal data that lasted until 31 December 2020. The purpose of this transition period was to allow time to negotiate a new relation to the EU. A transit period related was further extended until June 2021, waiting for the EU Commission's possible adequate decision. In light of this, the legislator in Norway adopted a temporary regulation, which states that the transfer of personal data to the United Kingdom is not considered a transfer to a third country under the Personal Data Act¹⁰¹. The regulation entered into force on 1 January 2021.

Articles 45.3 of the GDPR¹⁰² and Article 36.3 of the Law Enforcement Directive¹⁰³ grant the Commission the power to decide, by means of an implementing act, that a non-EU/EEA country ensures an adequate level of protection, i.e., a level of protection for personal data that is essentially equivalent to the level of protection within the EU. If a non-EU/EEA country has been found "adequate", transfers of personal data from the EU/EEA to the respective non-EU/EEA country can take place without being subject to any further conditions.

In anticipation of Brexit, a new domestic data privacy law called the UK-GDPR took effect on January 31, 2020. Together with the national laws, the UK-GDPR governs all processing of personal data from individuals located inside the UK and is based on the EU GDPR and the Law and Enforcement Directive (LED). The UK-GDPR provide parallel safeguards, individual rights, obligations for controllers and processors, rules on international transfers, supervision system and redress avenues to those existing under EU law. In addition, the draft decisions contain a comprehensive assessment of the conditions and limitations, including the supervision mechanisms and remedies applicable in the event of access to data by UK public authorities, specifically for law enforcement and national security purposes. Similar to what is provided in Article 89 GDPR, personal data processed for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes can be exempted from a number of listed provisions of the UK-GDPR. In regard to research, exemptions are probable to the provisions of the UK GDPR related to confirmation of processing, access to data and safeguards for third country transfers;

¹⁰¹ See <https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2020-12-30-3195> [accessed 26.05.2021]

¹⁰² GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-45-gdpr/> [accessed 26.05.2021]

¹⁰³ Eurlex, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016L0680> [accessed 26.05.2021]

right to rectification; restriction of processing and objection to processing. As regards archiving in the public interest, exemptions are also possible to the notification obligation regarding rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing and to the right to data portability.

It also worth noting that the UK is part of the European Convention of Human Rights and to “Convention 108” of the Council of Europe¹⁰⁴, the only binding multilateral instrument on data protection. This implies that the UK remains a member of the European “privacy family”.

The European Commission originally issued a draft decision stating that the UK will be a country with an “adequate level of protection” for the transfer of personal data. The decisions apply both under the Privacy Regulation (GDPR) and under the Law and Enforcement Directive (LED)¹⁰⁵. The latter entered into force at the same time as the GDPR and handles the processing of personal data related to criminal proceedings and prosecution, which are areas exempt from the GDPR. LED is also implemented in Norwegian law. The publication of the draft decisions is the beginning of a process towards their adoption. This involves obtaining an opinion from the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) and consent from a committee composed of representatives of the EU Member States. It is therefore highly probable that personal data may legally be transferred from the EU/EEA to the UK in the future.

Unlike other non-EU countries, EU law has shaped the UK’s data protection administration for decades. The approval will last for four years, and a new assessment of whether the level of privacy in the UK is sufficient for the transfers to continue beyond this will then be necessary. The UK’s surveillance legislation has been a part of the assessment and is considered to be within the GDPR. During the transition period, the Commission was carefully assessing the UK’s law and practice on personal data protection, including the rules on access to data by public authorities. The conclusion was that the UK ensures an essentially equivalent level of protection to the one guaranteed under the GDPR and the LED, as the EU Commission adopted two adequacy decisions for the UK the 28th of June 2021¹⁰⁶, one for GDPR¹⁰⁷ and one for LED¹⁰⁸.

This means that personal data can flow freely from EU/EEA to the UK in accordance with GDPR Chapter 5, having essential equivalent level of protection as guaranteed within EU/EEA¹⁰⁹.

¹⁰⁴ Eche.coe.int, https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/Convention_ENG.pdf [accessed 26.05.2021]

¹⁰⁵ See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02016L0680-20160504> [accessed 26.05.2021]

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¹⁰⁹ See https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_21_3183 [accessed 26.05.2021]

11 Concluding remarks

In this deliverable, the project group has studied the impact of the GDPR and some possible implications for sharing data. This has been done by describing and comparing national implementation of the GDPR in Norway, Denmark, Italy, Germany, Finland, and Sweden. In addition, interviews have been conducted with total fourteen researchers, from Norway, Denmark, and Italy. Open Science is about making scientific data, results, and processes accessible and reusable by all, as well as technologies and services behind them. Convincing researchers of the benefits of changing their practices and equipping them with the skills and knowledge needed to do so, is hence an important task.

Although one of the rationales behind the GDPR was to harmonize the legal framework for data processing to improve conditions for research and cross-border data flow, this has not necessarily been the case. The reason for this could be different national provisions from one country to another, but also the tendency for regulations (both national and the GDPR) to be interpreted strictly (for instance by the controller's DPO). This has led to insecurity in the research environment, thereby preventing data sharing from one controller to another. Results from this deliverable indicate that further work is necessary to improve cross-border data flow within Europe. As the report "Two years of the GDPR: Questions and answers"¹¹⁰ concludes, further support of harmonization and consistent implementation of the GDPR across the EU is warranted. This includes making sure that national legislation is fully in line with the GDPR.

The report also highlights that creating and using Codes of Conducts to facilitate harmonization across Member States and sectors is a valuable tool to ensure such harmonization. BBMRI-ERIC¹¹¹ has already taken the initiative and is currently developing A Code of Conduct for Health Research, where the aim is to reach a sector-specific code that explains how the GDPR applies in practice.

Most of the European countries this deliverable has examined so far have a national provision for the lawful processing of personal data for research purposes and archival purposes in the public interest. In Sweden, Finland, and Norway, this ensures a clear legal basis for processing personal data for these purposes. Denmark and Germany have not issued a similar provision in their respective national laws. However, both Denmark and Germany have issued a national legal basis for processing special categories of personal data, indicating that research and archival purposes are in the public interest.

Supplementary legislation is required in national laws to allow for the possibility of processing personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences by others than official authorities. There might be

¹¹⁰ European Commission (2020) "Two years of the GDPR: Questions and answers"

https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_20_1166 (downloaded 12.08.2020)

¹¹¹ Code of Conduct for Health Research: <http://code-of-conduct-for-health-research.eu/> (downloaded 01.10.2020)

concerns about sharing such data across borders, if the receiver is subject to a nation without national regulations permitting processing of criminal convictions or offences. Norway, Sweden, Denmark, and Finland have a general provision relating to criminal convictions and offences, which applies to research. The project team could not find any provision authorising processing these data in the German laws. Furthermore, it is our understanding that the Italian legislator has not given an explicit provision authorizing processing of personal data related to criminal convictions and offences.

Looking more closely at “archival purposes in the public interest and for research purposes” as a legal ground, there are differences in how national supplementation has been given. In summary, the terms and conditions for processing sensitive personal data varies from one country to another, but the common denominator in most countries is the importance of ensuring that the processing of special categories of personal data is subject to adequate safeguards in accordance with Article 89 (1)¹¹².

Even though ensuring that the processing of special categories of personal data is subject to adequate safeguards is a common denominator, what measures are considered necessary differs amongst the countries. This might be a hinder when sharing data, considering that lesser measures might be required in a receiving country as compared to what the controller demands. Hence, a code of conduct presenting common “minimum measures” for all countries should be warranted. Finland and Germany have made comprehensive lists of measures that they consider to be specific and suitable. It is the project groups’ understanding that the Italian legislator will soon present a list of appropriate safeguards when processing biometric, genetic and health data. Norway presupposes that safeguard should be individually assessed by the controller for each processing activity, and that this is done during consultation with a DPO before processing special categories of personal data. Sweden sees an ethical review as a suitable measure, whilst Denmark has not clarified in its national law what safeguards are considered appropriate.

This indicates that solutions to assessing specific safeguards pursuant to Article 89 (1)¹¹³ are quite varied. A mutual understanding as to what measures will satisfy the requirement of appropriate measures (“suitable, specific, technical, organizational”) pursuant to Article 89 (1), would therefore make sharing of research data across borders easier, hence possibly contribute to achieving the purpose of EOSC.

Going further with the work, SSHOC partners in Task 5.3 *Legal Issues of Innovative Data Access* plan to initiate work on a Social Sciences and Humanities Code of Conduct for research as a tool to ensure correct/harmonized legal application and demonstrate compliance with the GDPR. This will give the scientific research community a new opportunity to create a formal common framework to demonstrate

¹¹² GDPR, <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-89-gdpr/> [accessed 26.05.2021]

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compliance and facilitate harmonisation of data-sharing rules and practices e.g., in relation to research, making it easier to access and share research data that contains personal data.

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Please note that all Italian legal sources are based on oral communication and non-English versions, and that the legal situation might not be correctly presented in this report. These issues can be further explored in task 8.3 Legal and Ethical issues.

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www.eoscsecretariat.eu/eosc-governance/eosc-executive-board

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Annex – Interview guide

The project team has conducted interviews with researchers in three randomly selected countries (Denmark, Norway, and Italy), using the same interview guide. The interview guide was created by the task group and the questions were chosen in order to get a deeper understanding of the implications of the GDPR on the daily lives of the researchers. The point of view of researchers is important to examine the main impacts of the GDPR on the daily life of the researchers. The researchers were asked the following questions:

- Has the research process changed due to GDPR?
 - Can you access the same data?
 - Can you store the same data?
 - Can you share your data with relevant colleagues?
- Have you tried applying for research funds after the GDPR?
 - If so, how was it as compared to before?
 - If not, do you have colleagues who tried, and what was their experience?
- Have you tried applying for research funds after the GDPR?
 - If so, how was it as compared to before?
 - If not, do you have colleagues who tried, and what was their experience?
 - Have the implementation of DPO affected the research process?